

Incorporation of Peace Education in Existing Secondary Level Curriculum and Teachers' Practice

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Abstract

Peace education is a new discipline which is being introduced in the existing curriculum in the world. Peace education is mandatory for reducing violence and developing positive thinking. The major aim of this study was to examine the need of peace education and to investigate the

perception of teachers for incorporating peace education in existing curriculum at Secondary level. The study was descriptive in nature.

All the secondary school teachers (753) of district Attock were included in population of the study. Of these, 255 teachers were taken as a sample through a random sampling technique. The researcher employed a validated questionnaire for collecting data. The major findings showed that the teachers favored the inclusion of peace education as a compulsory subject at secondary level.

Key Words

Peace Education, Teachers, Curriculum, Secondary

Introduction

Peace education is a major tool for the reduction and control of conflicts. Peace education can create the consciousness among the individuals for understanding the threats of conflicts and violence. It eliminates the violence among people and promotes the constructive thinking (UNESCO, 2005). Peace Education transports enthusiasm and generates constructive efforts that empower the people for peace. If the secondary schools offer the creative energies and provide positive directions to the children and youth for fighting against the violent forces and conflicts they can pay a vital role in the future. It is an admitted fact that education is helpful in fostering the culture of peace among the people. It is the responsibility of the specialists and experts of peace education to discuss with the students of secondary schools on the peace related knowledge, skills and values for nurturing worldwide harmony and social justice. Peace is a tension free environment. Peace is defined by Harris (2004), as ensuring force for the presence of justice and the condition of the absence of structural and physical violence. Consequently it is mandatory that the school going children should be taught about the root causes of war, encounter and conflicts. They should be given the knowledge of global humanitarian laws, rights of human and different techniques of security and protection. They should learn the different skills and techniques for managing the conflicts and peace. It is observed that there is found the different conflicting situations in the secondary level schools. It is not a good sign in the educational institutions. Educational experts, parents of the children and the intellectuals can change the mind of the young generation. Vusumzi and Shumba (2013) have explained that the school going children who are involved in different conflicts and show their misbehaviors and rude behaviors with the others. They cannot contribute in any creative work and show poor performance in their studies. Educational institutions must provide the peaceful and tension free environment to the students for creative thinking and critical thinking. Education is considered a major tool of maintaining the peace. It condemns all those events and occurrences which destabilize the equality, justice and patience in the societies. It has been observed that different research scholars and educationists have explained the peace education in various point of view. Gutek (2006) defined peace education in these words and says that peace education is the careful effort to teach the children, youth and adult people about the root causes of conflicts and threats of wars and conflicts and they all are taught different skills for the promotion of peace culture. They are given knowledge that how they prevent from different conflicts in the world. According to Fisk (2000) in peace education children, youth and adults are given information

and knowledge about the different philosophies, morals, outlooks and, ethics of other people and new insights and perceptions are provided to the people for taking different steps for bring peace in the world. Oshita (2006) states that the purpose of peace education is not only teaching for culture of peace, it empowers the people for peace. In fact peace education is an approach of empowering people and giving knowledge and skills for managing the conflicts at all levels. Therefore Salomon (2002) described the chief actions and activities of peace education for altering the mind of the people. Basically peace education develops capacity building among the people for peace, now the people do not know how to handle the disputes and clashes with the negotiation process but also they are educated how to live in peace. In the same way, peace education is a mechanism of changing the attitudes of the people for avoiding conflicts, resolving conflicts and stimulating a culture of peace.

Statement of the Problem

This study was designed to investigate the perception of teachers for incorporating peace education in existing curriculum at Secondary level.

Objectives of the Study

1. To examine the perception of teachers regarding the need of peace education at Secondary level.
2. To investigate the perceptions of teachers for incorporating peace education in existing curriculum at Secondary level.

Research Questions

1. What are the perceptions of teachers regarding the need of peace education?
2. What are the perceptions of teachers for incorporating peace education in existing curriculum at Secondary level?

Review of Related Literature

There is a variety of literature on peace education. Peace education is a new educational discipline and specialized practice for the progress of educational programs for formation of peace everywhere in the world. There is a large number of peace education programs, with diverse styles, philosophies, and objectives. Some of the educational programs of peace education pursue the instant ending of physical violence in educational institutions and societies (Johnson and Johnson, 1996). The main goals of a value-oriented field of peace education is to nurture the peace related understanding, abilities and values among the students for creating peace environment (UNESCO, 1995). Reardon (2001) describes that peace education is the process to empower the people to relinquish the institution of conflict and eliminate with the standards of a peaceful society.

It has been explained by Jenkins that education for peace and education about peace are totally different from each other. Education for peace aims to give information, morals, activities and capacities to oppose violence (Jenkins, 2007). Peace education is unconcealed in its targets to challenge, apprehend, and fight violence. Peace education can be elaborated in two ways. In first way, he says that education should be about peace. In this way, the comprehensive meaning of peace, scope of peace, contents and problems related peace are taught. In the second way, he explains that education should be given for peace purpose and a culture of peace it is related to resolving difficulties or constructing peace, emphasizing on the contents of subjects and learning process so that education can build a stress free environment among the people (Sinlarat, 2002). Peace education will be more operative when the strategies for resolving conflicts are enthusiastically followed and demonstrated by the institutional atmosphere in which learners are trained (Baldo & Furniss, 1998).

In the modern and current world that the people of different cultures, races, civilizations, religions and societal classes are living together. It is predicted that tolerance is considered very important for creating a desirable environment of mutual respect and understanding of the people (Tatar, 2009). Now it is need to establish peace at international level which should be based on patience, social equality, and justice and sympathy .Peace education is a process, in which learners and teachers behaviors and attitudes are changed in the light of global values so that they treat to everyone with peacefully. That's why it is called solution -oriented atmosphere, where conflicted problems are resolved and violence and conflicts are eliminated (Salomon, 2002).

UNICEF (1999) defines that peace education is the procedure of providing peace related knowledge, morals and skills to the people, in this way, changes are occurred in the behaviors of the people for resolving the problems and preventing from conflicts. Harris (2004) has explained peace education into five following types:

- Education for conflict resolution
- Human rights education

- Developmental education
- Global education
- Environmental education

All these types can be considered the areas of peace education and these must be included in the curriculum and must be taught to the students for achieving the peace related targets. Thus, peace education is a representative of all the ethical values such as social unity, character, value, respect, tolerance or citizenship education and all these values can lead a society to a peaceful behavior. The improvement in peace education as an active social movement is the result of its energies that can affiliate and inspires dialogue among scholars, researchers, educators, government leaders and the uncountable public peacemakers committed to creating cultures of peace throughout the world as Lum explained (2013).

Peace education instills the moral values of self-respect, insight and other non-violent skills which are helpful for analyzing the global issues and problems. It also educates about the alternative security systems (Kester, 2009). Castro and Galance (2010) elaborated the following key themes of related peace education.

Holistic Concept of Peace

Peace is a calm environment. It is not only the nonappearance of physical violence. There is found good relationship and cooperative environment.

Conflict and Violence

Conflicts are the part of our lives. Conflicts can lead to the violence and in violence a man shows the behavior of using physical force for destroying and damaging someone or something.

Disarmament

Disarmament education is a process of teaching for reducing and abolishing war and weapons.

Nonviolence

Nonviolence helps the young people to provide the opportunities to discover nonviolence mechanism for solving the conflicts.

Resolution of conflicts

Learners are taught the operative ways of solving clashes and encounters peacefully.

Development Based on Justice

Learners need to comprehend that growth and progress is not financial growth only but also the unbiased sharing of its fruits.

Democratization

Learners are given the perception about the fundamental rights of the people in the state and everybody is given respect. In democracy all the people have equal rights.

Human Solidarity

Several unities bind together different religious, social, native and nationwide groups.

Sustainable Development

It is required that learners must get the knowledge of the interdependent liaison between people and the natural atmosphere. They must be aware about changes which are needed for ensuring the wellbeing of the societies (Igbuzor, 2010).

The prominent research scholar of peace education, Reardon (2001), stressed that the global agency is considered a fundamental capability of the scholars and practitioners of peace education. Different international peace education campaigns have aimed to focus the requirements of children and all students to produce a culture of peace education. The Declaration and Integrated framework for Action of UNESCO (2005) emphasized on education for peace, democracy and human rights and born out the remarkable hurdles to peace education such as viciousness, discrimination, prejudice, destructive nationalism as well as violation for human rights, religious bias

and the world gap between rich and poor. To pen of the document stressed the improvement of curriculum and pedagogy that would care for individuals who are responsible citizens Furthermore, its content should involve education for citizens at international level and insists on the construction of peace, human rights and finish to discrimination and the removal of bigotry(Hague Appeal for Peace, 1988).

There are three more international organizations that have shown provision for peace education are the global campaign for peace education, the Educational International and the Manifesto 2000.Hague Appeal for peace (HAP) supported, the global campaign for peace education and uses the UNESCO agenda which supports to create a culture of peace. According to the 21st Century, Hague agenda for peace and justice, we can easily achieve the culture of peace by the understanding of global problems and fight for honesty, fairness, non-violent act upon global criteria of human rights and equity grow social diversity and respect for all. Nevertheless, peace education can easily change the mental observation of an individual from violation of rules to a peaceful mind. The Educational International (EI) is working with UNESCO for the development of peace education throughout the world (UNESCO, 2009).

Methodology

The design of this study was descriptive. Cohen (2004) specifies that the descriptive technique is a good one for exploring the different problems. All the Secondary School Teachers (753) male and female of district Attock comprised the population of the study. Random sampling technique was used for selecting the sample of the study from the given population. The 255 teachers of total were taken as a sample. The researcher employed a validated questionnaire containing on 20 items for collecting data. It was prepared on five point Likert Scale. It was a self-developed instrument and it was developed by consulting the experts (Bandura, 2006). Experts were consulted for the purpose of validation of research instrument. Experts studied the whole questionnaire and gave their opinions about the statements. Some statements were eliminated from the questionnaire in the light of expert opinions and suggested statements were included in the questionnaire. Data were collected through correspondence and personal visits.

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed and presented in frequency and mean score.

Table 1. Perception of Teachers Regarding Need of Peace Education Perception of Teachers regarding need of Peace Education

Item No.	Statements		SA	A	UN	DA	SDA	Mean Score
1	Peace education is mandatory for stability of the country.	Frequency	200	20	10	15	10	4.5
		Percentage	78.4%	7.8 %	3.9%	5.8%	3.9%	
2	Peace education is an urgent need of the present conflicting situations.	Frequency	215	15	10	10	5	4.6
		Percentage	84.3%	5.8%	3.9%	3.9%	1.9%	
3	Peace education is necessary for reduction of violence.	Frequency	198	12	05	30	10	4.4
		Percentage	77.6%	4.7%	1.9%	11.7%	3.9%	
4	Peace education is compulsory for developing positive attitudes.	Frequency	170	50	20	07	08	4.4
		Percentage	66.6%	19.6%	7.8%	2.7%	3.1%	
5	Peace education is necessary for	Frequency	125	10	05	10	05	2.7

	promoting moral values.	Percentage	49%	3.9%	1.9%	3.9%	1.9%	
6	Peace education is mandatory for establishing cordial relations among the people.	Frequency	130	10	05	05	05	2.9
		Percentage	50.9%	3.9%	1.9%	1.9%	1.9%	
7	Peace education is compulsory for cultivating mutual respect.	Frequency	132	12	03	05	03	2.8
		Percentage	51.7%	4.7 %	1.1%	1.9%	1.1%	
8	Peace education should be introduced at secondary level.	Frequency	140	07	03	02	03	2.9
		Percentage	54.9%	2.7%	1.1%	0.7 %	1.1%	

Interpretation of Data Analysis (Table 1)

The analysis and interpretation of the data disclosed that the perception of the secondary school teachers is very positive about incorporating the peace education in the existing curriculum at secondary level. Table 1 row 1 showed that the 78.4% of the teachers gave responses in strongly agreed that peace education is mandatory for stability and protection of the country. Table 1 row 2 displayed that 84.3% of the teachers strongly agreed that conflicting situations are found everywhere in the country, so peace education is an urgent need of the present conflicting situation. Table 1 row 3 revealed that 77.6 % of total teachers gave their response in strongly agreed with the statement that peace education is necessary for reduction of violence. Table 1 row 4 presented that 66.6% of the teachers strongly agreed and 19.6% of the teachers were agreed that peace education is compulsory for developing positive attitudes. Table 1 row 5 depicted that 49% of the teachers favored that peace education is necessary for promoting moral values.

Table 1 row 6 displayed that almost 55% of the teachers supported in the form of agreed and strongly agreed that Peace education is mandatory for establishing cordial relations among the people. Table 1 row 7 illustrated that 51.7% of the teachers gave positive response in strongly agreed that peace education is compulsory for cultivating mutual respect. Table 1 row 8 depicted that 54.9% of the teachers favored that peace education should be introduced at secondary level.

Table 2. Perceptions of Tutors for incorporating peace education in existing curriculum.

Perceptions of Tutors for incorporating peace education in existing curriculum

Item No.	Statements	Results	SA	A	UNC	DA	SDA	Mean Score
1	Peace education as a subject should be incorporated at Secondary level.	Frequency	140	05	02	03	05	2.8
		Percentage	54.9%	1.9 %	0.7%	1.1%	1.9%	
2	Peace education may be added as a compulsory subject.	Frequency	130	15	02	07	01	2.8
		Percentage	50.9%	5.8%	0.7%	2.7%	0.3%	
3	Peace education may include as an elective subject.	Frequency	50	10	10	130	50	2.4
		Percentage	19.6%	3.9%	3.9%	50.9%	19.6%	
4	Peace education as a unit approach	Frequency	100	50	05	60	20	3.7

	may be introduced.	Percentage	47%	19.6%	1.9%	23.5%	7.8%	
5	As a unit, peace education may be added in textbook of 10 th Urdu.	Frequency	22	20	05	53	150	1.8
		Percentage	8.6%	7.8%	1.9%	20.7%	58.8%	
6	As a unit, peace education should be incorporated in textbook of 10 th Islamic Studies.	Frequency	200	20	05	20	10	4.4
		Percentage	78.4%	7.8%	1.9%	7.8%	3.9%	
7	Peace education may be as a unit in the textbook of 10 th English.	Frequency	10	10	05	80	155	1.6
		Percentage	3.9%	3.9 %	1.9%	31.3%	60.7%	
8	Peace education may be as a unit in the textbook of 10 th Pakistan studies.	Frequency	50	40	10	75	80	2.6
		Percentage	19.6%	15.6%	3.9%	29.4 %	31.3%	
9	Peace education should be introduced through integrated approach.	Frequency	230	10	05	05	05	4.7
		Percentage	90%	3.9%	1.9%	0.9 %	1.9%	
10	Peace education should be taught through an interdisciplinary approach.	Frequency	10	10	02	53	180	1.4
		Percentage	3.9%	3.9%	0.7%	20.7 %	75.5%	
11	Peace education may be incorporated in the disciplines of Sciences at Secondary level.	Frequency	05	05	05	20	220	1.2
		Percentage	86.2%	7.8%	1.9%	1.9 %	1.9%	
12	Peace education may be added in the disciplines of Social Sciences at Secondary level.	Frequency	230	10	02	08	05	4.7
		Percentage	90.1%	3.9%	0.7%	3.1 %	1.9%	

Interpretation of Data Analysis (Table 2)

Table 2 row 1 showed that 54.9 % of the teachers strongly agreed the peace education as a subject should be incorporated at Secondary level. Table 2 row 2 displayed that 50.9% of the teachers agreed that peace education should be added as a subject in the section of general education course as a compulsory subject. Table 2 row 3 revealed that 50.9% of the teachers disagreed for including peace education as an elective subject. Table 2 row 4 showed that 47% of the teachers favored that peace education should be introduced through unit approach at Secondary level. Table 2 row 5 indicated that 58.8% of the teachers strongly disagreed with the statement that peace education should be as a unit in the Secondary level textbook of Urdu. Table 2 row 6 exposed that 78.4% of the teachers favored that peace education should be as a unit in the Secondary level textbook of Islamic Studies. Table 2 row 7 disclosed that almost 92% % of the teachers disagreed that peace education should be as a unit in the Secondary level textbook of English. Table 2 row 8 unveiled that 61% of the teachers were disagreed that peace education should be as a unit in the Secondary level textbook of Pakistan studies. Table 2 row 9 indicated

that 94 % of the teachers favored that peace education should be introduced through integrated approach. Table 2 row 10 showed that 75.5% of the teachers disagreed with the statement that peace education should be taught through an interdisciplinary approach. Table 2 row 11 disclosed that 94% of teachers supported the statement that peace education may be added in the disciplines of Social Sciences at Secondary level. Table 2 row 12 depicted that 90 % of the teachers disagreed that peace education may be incorporated in the disciplines of Social Sciences at Secondary level.

Discussion

This study was planned to scrutinize the perception of teacher of district Attock (Punjab) regarding incorporating peace education in existing curriculum of distance education at Secondary level in Pakistan. These teachers have almost same qualification and they are working at Secondary level. The foremost aim of study was to examine the perception of teachers regarding need of peace education and incorporating peace education in existing curriculum at Secondary level. Through analysis of data, two major findings were identified. First, all the teachers gave same response that peace education is mandatory for reduction of violence and stability of the country. This finding is in line with the research study of Mishra (2015) "Implementing Peace Education in Schools: Perceptions of Stake Holders." who concluded by using semi-structured interview in his study that peace education should be taught in beginning classes of school and he also said that a comprehensive curriculum of peace education is mandatory for handling the violence and conflicts in the schools. Second major finding showed majority of the teachers favored that peace education would be included as a separate subject in the existing curriculum at Secondary level and rejected the unit approach of introducing peace education. It was also suggested that peace education must be the part of disciplines of social sciences for cultivating mutual respect and cordial relations among the people. The above second finding is in line with the studies of Onipe (2008) "Enhancing qualitative social studies education through the promotion of basic human values at school level." Wisdom and Imo (2010) conducted the research study related with co-curricular activities and improvement of peace education in schools who noted that inclusion of curricular activities and co-curricular activities related peace for promoting peace education is necessary. The above second finding is also in the line with the study of Ezeoba (2012) which was conducted at secondary level school curriculum of Nigeria. In his study, he concluded that the curriculum of Social Studies of secondary level of Nigeria needed to include peace related contents for the promotion of peace

Conclusion and Recommendations

It is concluded that peace education is mandatory for reducing the ratio of conflicts and stability of the country. Through giving the concept of peace education, conflicts can be reduced at all level. Majority of the respondents gave positive response that peace education is obligatory for establishing cordial relations and mutual respect among the people. However majority of the teachers recommended that peace education should be included as a compulsory subject at Secondary level. Majority of the teachers favored that peace education should be included through integrated approach and majority of the teachers rejected the statement that peace education should be included as a unit in the Secondary level textbooks of English, Urdu and Pakistan Studies. However majority of the teachers favored that peace education can be included as a unit in the Secondary level textbook of Islamic Studies. Majority of the participants of the study showed their response in favor that peace education as a subject should be a part of disciplines of social sciences. However the participants of the study gave their response that peace should not be a part of disciplines of sciences. It was recommended that Peace education may be imparted at Secondary level. Peace education related topics may be integrated in all subjects. Peace education may put as a compulsory subject in existing curriculum of Secondary level. Peace education may be introduced through interdisciplinary approach. Peace education may be included as elected subject in the disciplines of social sciences. Teachers may be given the training of pedagogical strategies for peace education. The content materials of curriculum may be consisted of activities related peace education. Seminars and sessions may be arranged for introducing peace education as a new subject.

References

- Bandura, A. (2006). Guide for constructing self-efficacy scales. *Self-efficacy beliefs of adolescents*, 5(1), 307-337.
- Baldo, M., & Furniss, E., (1998). 'Integrating life skills into the primary curriculum'. New York, UNICEF
- Castro L.N., & Galance J.N.(2010). Peace Education: A Pathway to a culture of Peace. Quezon City: Miriam College.
- Cohen, L. (2004). A consumers' republic: The politics of mass consumption in postwar America. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 31(1), 236-239.
- Ezeoba, K. O. (2012). Strategies for integrating peace education into social studies curriculum for junior secondary (Basic 7-9) schools in Nigeria. *African Research Review*, 6(3), 218-231.
- Fisk, L. (2000). Shaping visionaries: Nurturing peace through education. Patterns of conflict, paths to peace, 159-193.
- Getek, G. L. (2006). American education in a global society: International and Comparative perspectives. Long Grove, IL: Waveland Press.
- Hague Appeal for Peace (1998) The Hague Agenda for Peace and Justice for the 21st Century. UN ref A/54/98.
- Harris, I. (2004). Peace education theory *Journal of Peace Education*. 1(1): 5-20.
- Johnson, D. W., & Johnson, R. T. (1996). Conflict resolution and peer mediation programs in elementary and secondary schools: A review of the research. *Review of Educational research*, 66(4), 459-506.
- Igbuzor, O. (2010). Electoral violence in Nigeria. Asaba, Action Aid Nigeria.
- Jenkins, J. (2007). English as a lingua franca: Attitude and identity. Oxford University Press.
- Kester, K. (2005). Education for Peace: Content, Form and Structure: Mobilizing Youth for Civic Engagement. *The Peace and Conflict Review*, 4(2).
- Lum, B J., (2013). Peace Education: Past, Present and Future. *Journal of Peace Education*. 10 (2). 121-123
- MISHRA, L. (2015). Implementing Peace Education In Secondary Schools Of Odisha: Perception Of Stake Holders. *Sakarya University Journal of Education*, 5(2), 47-54.
- Ncontsa, V. N., & Shumba, A. (2013). The nature, causes and effects of school violence in South African high schools. *South African Journal of Education*, 33(3).
- Onipe, O.A. (2008). Enhancing qualitative social studies education through the promotion of basic human values at the junior secondary school level. Nigeria *Journal of Curriculum Studies Special edition 2008*, 15-21.
- Oshita, M. (2006, June). Motion-capture-based avatar control framework in third-person view virtual environments. In Proceedings of the 2006 ACM SIGCHI international conference on Advances in computer entertainment technology (p.2). ACM.
- Reardon, T., & Farina, E. (2001). The rise of private food quality and safety standards: illustrations from Brazil. *The International Food and Agribusiness Management Review*, 4(4), 413-421.
- Salomon, G.N. (2002). "The Nature of Peace Education: Not All Programs are Created Equal" In *Peace Education: The Concept, Principles, and Practices around the world*, edited by G.Salomon and B. Nevo, 3-13. Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates Publishers.
- Sinlarat, P. (2002). Private Tutoring for High School Students in Thailand. Office of the National Education.
- Tatar, M. (2009). *Enchanted hunters: The power of stories in childhood*. WW Norton & Company.
- UNESCO. (2005). Decade of Education for Sustainable Development: 2005-2014. Draft International Implementation Scheme.
- UNICEF. (1993). Peace Education in UNICEF. Retrieved on 16th July, 2016 from <http://www.unicef.org/education/files/peaceEducation.pdf>.
- UNESCO. (2009). International technical guidance on sexuality education: An evidence-informed approach for schools, teachers and health educators. II.
- Wisdom, I.J., & Imo, M.O. (2010). Literacy inco-curricular programmes and enhancement of peace education in schools. *Nigeria Journal of Curriculum Studies* 17(3) 128-136